

MODELLING AND TESTING OF THE SNAP-THROUGH PROCESS OF CROSS-PLY COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

Bi-stable response of unsymmetric cross-ply square composite plates supported at four points is modelled when a point load is applied at the centre of the plate. The model is based on the Rayleigh-Ritz technique, including non-linear von Kármán strain components, non-uniform curvatures and uniform through-the-thickness normal strain. The numerical analysis has been carried out step by step, by small increments of the applied load. Experiments in four $[0/90]_T$ carbon/epoxy laminates have been carried out in a test configuration that fulfils the requirements of the model. The multi-event snap-through and intermediate equilibrium positions have been experimentally observed and recorded. The initial snap-through and snap-back load-displacement curves have been experimentally determined and compared to those corresponding to the proposed model.

1 INTRODUCTION

Asymmetric cross-ply laminates have residual curvatures at Room Temperature (RT) due to the elevated temperatures experienced during manufacturing. These laminates can have two stable shapes at RT. This is known as the snap-through phenomenon. In snap-through the specimen is forced to snap from the first to the second equilibrium shape and in snap-back the specimen snaps from the second to the first equilibrium shape.

Bi-stable composite laminates have been proposed as a choice to generate novel morphing structures. Hyer et al.[1] predicted the cured shapes of bi-stable laminates at RT developing an approximate theory based on the Rayleigh-Ritz technique assuming strain and displacement fields, and minimizing the Total Potential Energy (TPE). They used low order polynomial functions, linear elastic constitutive equations and nonlinear relations of von Kármán strains. Potter et al. [2] experimentally analysed the bifurcation of unsymmetric plates and they observed that the snap-through phenomenon was not a simple event and it occurred as a result of changes in curvatures.

The snap process of a cross-ply laminate triggered by a vertical force and supported at four points has been recently analysed using the Rayleigh-Ritz technique [3]. The aim of this work is to propose a model to study snap-through and snap-back in square cross-ply laminates supported at four points and acted on by a concentrated load, based on the Rayleigh-Ritz technique and the minimization of the TPE. To evaluate the strain energy of the whole laminate, four displacement fields are proposed: one corresponding to points among supports, and the others for points outside the supports. The model also considers a uniform through-the-thickness strain and non-uniform curvatures including the novel concept of mechanical curvatures [4]. To validate the present approach, experimental tests have been carried out in cross-ply laminates supported on 4 rods and acted on by a central force, as it is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Test configuration.

2 ANALYTIC APPROACH

2.1 Motivation

In the first approach to the problem of determination of the displacement field due to residual stresses in cross-ply laminates, Hyer [1] used the polynomial form of the vertical displacement field obtained by the Classical Lamination Theory (CLT), considering that the coefficients were unknown. Geometrically non-linear terms of von-Kármán were included in the mid-plane strains according to:

$$\begin{aligned}\varepsilon_x^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial x} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \right)^2 \\ \varepsilon_y^0 &= \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial y} + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y} \right)^2 \\ \gamma_{xy}^0 &= \frac{\partial u^0}{\partial y} + \frac{\partial v^0}{\partial x} + \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial x} \frac{\partial w^0}{\partial y}\end{aligned}\quad (1)$$

The unknown coefficients of the polynomials were determined by minimizing the TPE of the laminate. Following the same idea of Hyer, in the present study the polynomial forms of the vertical displacement field has been obtained based on a previous approach concerning a plate supported at four points and acted on by a central load, valid for small displacements.

2.2 Displacement and strain fields

Mujika [5] developed an analytical approach of multidirectional laminates when a vertical force was applied at the centre of the laminate and the laminate was supported at four points. The laminate was divided into four parts, A, B, C, D as shown in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Upper view of the plate used in the analytical approach of Mujika.

Due to central symmetry the displacement field of A, D parts and B, C parts were the same. The out-of-plane displacement terms of a multidirectional laminate at any point of parts A, B were determined by using normalized coordinates placed at the corner of the laminate. In the case of a square cross-ply laminate it is supported at four points being the reactions at each support $F/4$. Furthermore, the hygrothermal twisting curvature and the bending twisting compliance coupling coefficients are null. Therefore, the displacement field of all parts is the same, and it is obtained by adding the effects of bending w_M and the hygrothermal effects w_{HT} , as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{96}{FL^2} w_M(x_0, y_0) &= 2d_{xx}(-4x_0^3 + 3x_0) + 6d_{xy}g(-x_0^2 + x_0 - y_0^2 + y_0) + d_{yy}g(-4y_0^3 + 3y_0) \\ w_{HT}(x_0, y_0) &= \frac{L^2}{4} \kappa_x^{HT}(x_0 - x_0^2) + \frac{L^2}{4} \kappa_y^{HT}(y_0 - y_0^2) \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where F is the applied load; L is the distance between the supports; $g=L/L'$ is the span-to-overall-length ratio; d_{ij} , ($i, j = x, y$) are the compliance coefficients; $\kappa_x^{HT}, \kappa_y^{HT}$ are the curvatures when only hygrothermal effects are considered.

The out-of-plane-displacement over a quarter of the laminate valid for coordinates that vary among supports, including bending and hygrothermal effects, is named w_l^0 . It is obtained after two changes of coordinates for obtaining normalized coordinates placed at the centre and it is expressed using generic coefficients c_1, c_2, c_3, c_4 as:

$$w_l^0(x, y) = \frac{1}{2}(c_1x^2 + c_2y^2) + \frac{1}{6}(c_3x^3 + c_4y^3) \quad \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq x_{ct}, \quad 0 \leq y \leq y_{ct} \quad (3)$$

In cross-ply laminates supported at four points with an external force applied at the centre, the position of the contact points vary when the force increases. Fig. 3 shows the initial coordinates of the contact point in the undeformed and deformed configurations. The coordinates of the contact point are named x_{ct}, y_{ct} . The x axis is curvilinear and x_{ct} is measured on the curved surface between the origin and the contact point of the laminate with the support. Due to the change of the position of the contact points, the part out-of-supports in the x direction increases, as it is shown in Fig. 3, while in the y direction can be assumed to remain constant, being a half of the distance between the two contact points.

Figure 3: Initial coordinate of the contact point in undeformed and deformed configurations.

In the laminate there are four zones defined by the lines $x = x_{ct}$ and $y = y_{ct}$ as it is shown in Fig. 4: the central part is the zone I, the cantilever in x direction is the zone II, the cantilever in y direction is the zone III and the intersection between both cantilevers is the zone IV. Fig. 5 shows these domains

and the mechanical moments M_x and M_y , acting in each zone. Furthermore, hygrothermal moments act on the four zones.

Figure 4: Four zones defined by the lines $x = x_{ct}$ and $y = y_{ct}$.

The displacement field in the zone I is given in Eq.(3). For obtaining the displacement fields for the zones II, III it is applied the same calculation technique as it was used by Mujika [5]. The displacements in zone IV are only due to hygrothermal effects. The vertical displacements have to satisfy continuity of displacements and their derivatives up to third order along boundary lines of the different zones. Then, the vertical displacements defined in the whole laminate shown in Fig. 4 are:

$$\begin{aligned}
 w_I^0(x, y) &= \frac{1}{2}(c_1 x^2 + c_2 y^2) + \frac{1}{6}(c_3 x^3 + c_4 y^3) & \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq x_{ct}, 0 \leq y \leq y_{ct} \\
 w_{II}^0(x, y) &= -\frac{1}{2}c_3 x_{ct}^2 x + \frac{1}{2}(c_1 + c_3 x_{ct}) x^2 + \frac{1}{2}c_2 y^2 + \frac{1}{6}c_4 y^3 & \text{for } x_{ct} \leq x \leq \frac{L}{2}, 0 \leq y \leq \frac{L}{2} \\
 w_{III}^0(x, y) &= -\frac{1}{2}c_4 y_{ct}^2 y + \frac{1}{2}(c_2 + c_4 y_{ct}) y^2 + \frac{1}{2}c_1 x^2 + \frac{1}{6}c_3 x^3 & \text{for } 0 \leq x \leq x_{ct}, y_{ct} \leq y \leq \frac{L}{2} \\
 w_{IV}^0(x, y) &= \frac{1}{2}(c_1 + c_3 x_{ct}) x^2 + \frac{1}{2}(c_2 + c_4 y_{ct}) y^2 & \text{for } x_{ct} \leq x \leq \frac{L}{2}, y_{ct} \leq y \leq \frac{L}{2}
 \end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

In the present proposal, a uniform through-the-thickness strain $\varepsilon_z = d$ is also considered. The mid-plane strains, due to orthogonal design of square plates are assumed to be:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \varepsilon_x^0(x, y) &= c_5 + c_6 x^2 + c_7 y^2 + c_8 xy \\
 \varepsilon_y^0(x, y) &= c_9 + c_7 x^2 + c_6 y^2 - c_8 xy
 \end{aligned} \tag{5}$$

The mid-plane displacement functions are obtained by integration from Eq. (5). They are necessary for obtaining mid-plane shear strains. Cantera et al. [4] followed the indication of Tiersten [6] about the kinematics of deformation, considering non-uniform mechanical curvatures $\kappa_x^{Mech}, \kappa_y^{Mech}$. These curvatures in a first approach are given by:

$$\kappa_x^{Mech} = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial x^2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)^2 \right] \quad \kappa_y^{Mech} = -\frac{\partial^2 w}{\partial y^2} \left[1 + \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial y} \right)^2 \right] \tag{6}$$

Considering the mid-plane normal strain terms of Equation (5), the mid-plane shear strains and the mechanical curvatures given in Eq. (6), the strain field of the model is given in terms of 13 unknown coefficients.

2.3 Displacements due to thermal stresses

The strain energy density φ_i of each zone of the laminate is determined considering each strain field. In terms of the stiffness matrix [C] it is given in abbreviated form by:

$$\varphi_i = \sum_{k=1}^2 \left(\frac{1}{2} \{ \varepsilon_i \}^T [C]^k \{ \varepsilon_i \} - \{ \varepsilon_i \}^T [C]^k \{ \alpha \}^k \Delta T \right) \quad i = I, II, III, IV \tag{7}$$

The stiffness coefficients C_{ij} are calculated in terms of engineering constants. Each layer is assumed to be transversally isotropic, with the 2-3 plane as a plane of isotropy. Therefore, the subscripts 2 and 3 are interchangeable. Without considering out-of-plane shear relations, the stress-strain relation in the principal directions of orthotropy of the lamina k is given by:

$$\begin{Bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 \\ \tau_6 \end{Bmatrix}_{(k)} = \begin{bmatrix} C_{11} & C_{12} & C_{12} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{22} & C_{23} & 0 \\ C_{12} & C_{23} & C_{22} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & C_{66} \end{bmatrix}_{(k)} \begin{Bmatrix} \varepsilon_1 \\ \varepsilon_2 \\ \varepsilon_3 \\ \gamma_6 \end{Bmatrix} \quad (8)$$

Before applying the force, the laminate is curved due to residual stresses. Then the potential work of the external force is null and the first variation of the TPE, named δII is given by:

$$\delta II = \delta U = 0 \quad \delta II = \frac{\partial U}{\partial e_j} \delta e_j \equiv 0 \quad j = 1, 13 \quad (9)$$

Eq. (9) is a system of 13 non linear equations. It is solved with the aid of Mathematica (Wolfram). The mean curvatures and the initial angles measured from the centre of the laminate to the contact point of supports, named $\theta_x^{01}, \theta_y^{01}$ are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa_x^{0m} &= \frac{2}{L} \int_0^{\frac{L}{2}} \kappa_x^0 dx & \kappa_y^{0m} &= \frac{2}{L} \int_0^{\frac{L}{2}} \kappa_y^0 dx; \\ \theta_x^{01} &= \arcsin\left(\frac{L_s}{2} \kappa_x^{0m}\right) & \theta_y^{01} &= \arcsin\left(\frac{L_s}{2} \kappa_y^{0m}\right) \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

where L_s is the distance between the centres of two support rods, shown in Fig. 3. Considering the spherical form of radius r of support rods, corrected angles θ_x^0, θ_y^0 are obtained according to:

$$\theta_x^0 = \arcsin\left(\left(\frac{L_s}{2} + r \sin\theta_x^{01}\right) \kappa_x^{0m}\right) \quad \theta_y^0 = \arcsin\left(\left(\frac{L_s}{2} + r \sin\theta_y^{01}\right) \kappa_y^{0m}\right) \quad (11)$$

Due to thermal residual stresses, the initial shape of the cross-ply laminate could be approximated to a cylinder. Taking into account Eqs. (10) and (11), the coordinates of the initial contact point can be determined as:

$$x_{ct}^0 = \frac{\theta_x^0}{\kappa_x^{0m}} \quad y_{ct}^0 = \frac{\theta_y^0}{\kappa_y^{0m}} \approx \frac{L_s}{2} \quad (12)$$

When the main curvature is κ_x , it can be assumed that the y coordinate of the contact point y_{ct} does not change, being $y_{ct} = \frac{L_s}{2}$.

2.4 Displacements due to the load application

When the load is applied at the centre of the laminate, the expression of the first variation of the TPE is given by:

$$\delta II = \delta U - \delta W_F = 0 \quad \delta II = \frac{\partial II}{\partial e_j} \delta e_j \equiv 0 \quad j = 1, 13 \quad (13)$$

where δW_F is the first variation of the potential work of the applied load, or virtual work. As the origin of the reference system is located at the centre of the laminate, it is assumed that the plate is fixed at the centre and that supports are vertically moving during the test. The applied load causes equal vertical reaction forces at the contact points. The virtual work δW_F of applied forces in Eq. (22) is determined by the virtual vertical displacement given by:

$$\delta\Pi = \delta U - \delta W_F = 0 \quad \delta\Pi = \frac{\partial\Pi}{\partial e_j} \delta e_j \equiv 0 \quad j=1, 13 \quad (14)$$

The TPE is evaluated step by step. At step i the coordinate of the contact point x_{ct}^i is unknown, but it is known at the previous step x_{ct}^{i-1} . The applied force at step i F^i increases from the previous step a small increment ΔF^i . The strain energy and the potential work of the forces at step i are evaluated at x_{ct}^{i-1} .

In the case of bending of beams and plates, the vertical displacement w is not in the vertical line of the corresponding x coordinate due to horizontal displacements. Fig. 5 shows half of a level curve, where unprimed letters represent points in the undeformed configuration and primed letters represent points in the deformed configuration. As it is shown in Fig. 5, the coordinate x corresponds to the undeformed configuration and h_x is the horizontal projection in the deformed configuration. According to the kinematics of deformation shown in Fig. 5, the element PQ in the undeformed configuration moves to the element P'Q' in the deformed configuration, without changing its length.

Figure 5: Undeformed and deformed configurations in bending problems.

The relation between x and h_x can be derived when PQ is a differential element dx and it is given by:

$$dh_x = dx + \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} dx \quad (15)$$

The value of the angle θ_x^i in step i can be inferred from Fig. 6 estimated at the contact point x_{ct}^{i-1}, y_{ct} :

$$\sin \theta_x^i = \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)_{\substack{x=x_{ct}^{i-1} \\ y=y_{ct}}} \quad \cos \theta_x^i = 1 + \left(\frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \right)_{\substack{x=x_{ct}^{i-1} \\ y=y_{ct}}} \quad (16)$$

Figure 6: Differential triangle that relates h_x and x .

Integrating Eq. (15) it results:

$$\int_0^{h_x} dh_x = \int_0^{x_{ct}} dx + \int_0^{x_{ct}} \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} dx \quad (17)$$

From Eq. (17) the coordinate of the contact point at step i , named x_{ct}^i , is given by:

$$x_{ct}^i = h_x^i - u^i(x_{ct}^i, y_{ct}^i) \quad (18)$$

The position of the contact points of the laminate at undeformed and deformed configurations at step i , and step $i+1$, named x_{ct}^i, x_{ct}^{i+1} , are represented in Fig. 7. The coordinate h_x and the displacement u of each point are also included.

Figure 7: Position of the contact point at step i and $i+1$.

In step i , as it is shown in Fig. 8 the horizontal distance h_x^i measured from the centre of the laminate to the contact point is given by:

$$h_x^i = \frac{L_s}{2} + r \sin \theta_x^i \quad (19)$$

Figure 8: Estimation of the horizontal distance h_x^i at step i .

In step i , the derivative $\frac{\partial w}{\partial x}$ and the in-plane displacement u^i are evaluated at the previous the contact point x_{ct}^{i-1}, y_{ct} . Replacing Eq. (19) in Equation (18) and considering Equation (16) x_{ct}^i at step i is given by:

$$x_{ct}^i = \frac{L_s}{2} + r \left(\frac{\partial w}{\partial x} \right)_{\substack{x=x_{ct}^{i-1} \\ y=y_{ct}}} - u^i(x_{ct}^{i-1}, y_{ct}) \quad (20)$$

3 EXPERIMENTAL

3.1 Testing procedure

Cross-ply laminates of Hexcel Composites T6T/F593 carbon/epoxy unidirectional prepregs were manufactured in a hot press. A first curing state at 120°C during 45 minutes was followed by a curing at 180°C during 120 minutes. The laminate was air cool-down and it curled into a cylindrical shape. After manufacturing, the laminates were cut with a diamond saw to obtain squared laminates of side-length L . Before testing, in order to avoid humidity absorption, they were kept in an oven at 120 °C during 72 h. The nominal thickness of the laminates was 0.45 mm.

Four square specimens were tested in order to determine the load–displacement curve of the snap-through and snap-back. The side-lengths of specimens S1, S2, S3 and S4 were, respectively (mm): 120, 145, 178, 195. A universal testing machine MTS that incorporated a 250 N load cell with a load application rod, and a support plate with four supporting rods was used, as shown in Fig. 1. The four supporting rods, finished in a 12 mm-diameter polished semi- sphere, were screwed to a 15 mm thick aluminium plate. Across the surface of the plate there was a 14 x 14 array of drilled holes, 10 mm away. By placing the supporting rods in the holes, the distances among supports were obtained for each laminate. The displacement rate of the tests was 20 mm/min. The distance among the centres of the supporting rods L_s varied from 100 to 160 mm. The experimental procedure was carried out according to the following steps:

1. In order to determine the maximum displacements of the curved laminates before testing, a glass plate of thickness t was laid over the four support rods. The top surface of the reference glass plate was adopted as 0 displacement in the testing system.
2. After removing the glass plate, the laminate was laid over the supports to determine the initial displacement δ^0 of the middle point of the laminate, due only to hygrothermal effects. The value provided by the machine was corrected adding the thickness of the glass plate.
3. Before starting the test, it was applied a preload of 0.1 N and that point was defined as 0 displacement for the testing system.
4. Mechanical test was carried out in order to obtain the load-displacement curves.

Each specimen was alternatively tested 5 times snap-through and 5 times snap-back, showing good repeatability in terms of peak load, displacements and energy. For all specimens, the experimental relations between maximum load of snap-through and snap-back were greater than 1.

Fig. 9 shows experimental load-displacement curves corresponding to snap-through of the four tested specimens. The snap-back curves were similar. Initially the load-displacement response was essentially linear up to a point where the curve becomes increasingly non-linear and reached a peak value. In this peak load, the laminate started losing its stability. The area under the curve indicates the energy required to snap from a stable geometry to other. This energy represents the barrier that must be overcome to reach the bifurcation.

Figure 9: Experimental load-displacement curves of all specimens.

In Fig. 9, intermediate states where the applied load remained constant or it had small variation are shown, while the out-of-plane displacements varied quite a few millimetres. These states were separated by abrupt changes in the load-displacement curves. In Fig. 10 a photograph of the deformed specimens corresponding to the mentioned intermediate state are shown.

Figure 10: Photograph corresponding to an abrupt change in the load-displacement curve.

These states were intermediates snap-through and snap-back positions prior to reach the final cylindrical shape. The multi-event snap-through and back and intermediate equilibrium positions are associated with quasi-horizontal parts of the load-displacement curves as shown in Fig. 9. As the length-size of the laminate increased, the load jumps to intermediate equilibrium positions were more pronounced. In all specimens, the instabilities at snap-through were greater than at snap-back phenomenon.

3.2 Calibration of the model

It was experimentally observed that maximum displacement due to hygrothermal effects before applying any force was different previous snap-through and snap-back tests. This section presents a method for calibrating the model, based on experimental values of the displacements previous to snap-through and snap-back tests. These displacements have been determined according to the procedure explained in section 3.1. The possible thickness difference of layers in a cross-ply laminate named h_{90} and h_0 , implies that the configuration before snap-through and before snap-back may have different initial displacements. This could be one of the reasons of the differences between load-displacement curves at snap-through and snap-back. Therefore, the difference of thickness should be taken into account in the modelling.

When a snap-through test was finished, the laminate had to be flipped to start the snap-back test. The layer at 90° in snap-through became the layer at 0° in snap-back and the layer at 0° in snap-through became the layer at 90° in snap-back. Theoretically, the value of the thickness ratio in the $[0/90]_T$ cross-ply should be 0.5. The model was calibrated by adjusting this thickness ratio, named f . The initial values of w predicted by the proposed model depend on the thickness distribution, and

therefore, it is possible to predict different values of w when f varies from 0.5 to 0.55. As the ratio between the experimental values of the initial displacements at snap-through and snap-back is known, the goal was to obtain a value of f in order to adjust the model to obtain the same ratio for the numerical displacements.

3.3 Experiment-model comparison

In order to compare modelled and measured displacements, the reference systems used and the position of the contact point should be taken into account. On the one hand, the origin of the reference system of the model is placed at the center of the laminate at step i , while the experimental displacements measured by the testing system are referred to the centre of the laminate at step 0, when no force is applied. On the other hand, the position of the contact points between the supports and the laminate change during the test.

Modelled displacements at step 0 w^0 and at step i w^i and experimental displacements δ^i are shown in Fig.11. δ^i is the vertical displacement at step i determined following the experimental procedure explained in section 3.1.

Figure 11: Modelled and experimental displacements.

The relation between δ^i and the modelled displacements w_0 , w_i and the angles θ_x^0, θ_x^i is given by:

$$\delta^i = w^0 \left(x_{ct}^0, \frac{L_x}{2} \right) - w^i \left(x_{ct}^i, \frac{L_x}{2} \right) - r (\cos \theta_x^i - \cos \theta_x^0) \quad (21)$$

Therefore, the displacement δ^i given by Eq. (21) is used to compare model and experimental displacements. The non-linear system can be solved in a stable laminate. When local instabilities appear, usually near the peak load, the laminate loses its stability, and therefore, the system can not be solved. Therefore, the modelled curve is determined up to the maximum load, and the experimental-model comparison is carried out up to the peak load of the curve. The modelled load-displacements curves are obtained step by step for each laminate at snap-through and snap-back. The experimental and modelled load-displacement curves of S1 corresponding to snap-through is shown in Fig. 12.

Figure 12: Experimental and modeled load-displacement curve.

Modelled and experimental curves have similar displacement at the peak load. Modelled peak loads are greater than the experimental ones. Comparisons in terms of peak load, displacement at peak load and slope of the load-displacement curve prior to initial instabilities corresponding to snap-through are shown in Fig. 13.

Figure 13: Comparison between model and experiments in snap-through and snap-back: (a) peak load; (b) displacement at peak load; (c) slope of the curve load-displacement.

Modelled peak loads are greater than the experimental ones. On the one hand, this could be due to the lower precision of the system of equations at the surroundings of the maximum load due to instabilities. On the other hand, the model is based on displacements, which provide a model that is stiffer than the experimental values obtained because the assumed admissible displacements do not include all those possible.

In the specimens 1, 2 and 3, the average of the ratio of peak loads of the model respect to the test is 1.23 ± 0.08 at snap-through and 1.52 ± 0.26 at snap-back, and in the laminate 4 they are 1.54 and 2.34, respectively.

The predictions of the displacements at peak loads are close to the experimental values obtained in the tests. In the specimens 1, 2 and 3 the average ratio of displacement at peak load of the model

respect to the experimental values are 0.88 ± 0.007 at snap-through and 0.963 ± 0.82 at snap-back. In the laminate 4 they are 1.02 and 1.42, respectively. The slopes of the modelled load-displacements curves are greater than the experimental ones. Results of specimen 4 does not follow the same trend that the other laminates, probably because specimen 4 presents the largest side-length-to-thickness ratio.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

A novel procedure of modeling snap-through of square cross-ply composites acted on by a central load and supported at four points is proposed. The Rayleigh-Ritz technique has been used, taking as unknowns the coefficients of the polynomial form of a previous analytic solution valid for small displacements. Then, the principle of total potential energy has been used for determining the unknown parameters. The strain energy at each zone and the work of applied forces is calculated at each load step.

For validation, mechanical tests corresponding to snap-through and snap-back have been carried out. The multi-event snap-through and back and intermediate equilibrium positions have been captured in the load-displacement curves and shown in photographs.

The initial snap-through and snap-back displacements were experimentally determined and compared with the model in order to estimate the layer thickness distribution of the cross-ply laminate. The differences that appeared in snap-through and snap-back phenomena could be explained by the possible thickness differences between the layers at 0° and at 90° .

The load-displacements curves predicted by the model are stiffer than the experimental ones. Among other factors, this could be related to the fact that the present approach is based on displacements. Then, the assumed admissible displacements do not include all those possible resulting in a model that is stiffer than the actual one.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.W. Hyer, The room temperature shapes of 4-layer unsymmetric cross-ply laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **16**, 1982, pp. 318-40.
- [2] K. Potter, P. Weaver, A.A. Seman and S. Shah, Phenomena in the bifurcation of unsymmetric composite plates, *Composites Part A-Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **38**, 2007, pp. 100-106.
- [3] M.A. Cantera, J.M. Romera, I. Adarraga and F. Mujika, Modelling and testing of the snap-through process of bi-stable cross-ply composites, *Composite Structures*, **120**, 2015, pp. 41-52.
- [4] M.A. Cantera, J.M. Romera, I. Adarraga and F. Mujika, Modelling of [0/90] laminates subject to thermal effects considering mechanical curvature and through-the-thickness strain. *Composite Structures*, 110, 2014, pp. 77-87.
- [5] F. Mujika, A novel approach for the three-point flexure test of multidirectional laminates, *Journal of Composite Materials*, **46**, 2012, pp. 259-274.
- [6] H. Tiersten, On the derivation of the equation for the deflection of thin beams, *Mathematics and Mechanics of Solids*, 2006(11), pp. 176-180.